

Abstract

Effectiveness of Acupuncture on Functional Capacity and Health-Related Quality of Life in Patients Undergoing Haemodialysis.

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Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a global health challenge associated with high morbidity and significant socioeconomic burden. Patients undergoing maintenance haemodialysis (HD) often suffer from severe physical deterioration, including skeletal muscle atrophy, reduced functional capacity, and impaired health-related quality of life (HRQOL). These limitations diminish autonomy and long-term survival, necessitating safe, integrative therapeutic strategies.

Objective: This research programme evaluated the efficacy of acupuncture as a complementary intervention to improve functional capacity and HRQOL in patients with advanced CKD undergoing haemodialysis.

Methods: A patient-assessor-blinded, parallel-group, randomised controlled trial (RCT) was conducted. Participants were allocated to verum acupuncture (VA), sham acupuncture (SA), or a non-

acupuncture waiting-list control group. Functional capacity was measured using the 6-Minute Walk Test (6MWT), 30-Second Sit-to-Stand Test (STS-30), and Handgrip Strength (HGS). HRQOL was assessed via the validated KDQOL-SF™ 1.3, analysing physical, mental, and disease-specific domains. The study also examined dose-response effects by comparing different treatment-frequency regimens.

Results: Verum acupuncture yielded statistically and clinically significant improvements in functional capacity and peripheral muscle strength compared to sham and control groups. Large effect sizes were observed for walking capacity and lower-limb strength, with moderate effects for handgrip strength; these improvements were partially maintained at a 12-week follow-up. Notably, treatment frequency did not significantly alter outcomes, suggesting once-weekly sessions are as effective as intensive protocols. Regarding HRQOL, VA produced significant short-term gains in physical and mental health, symptom burden, and sleep quality. However, these benefits were not sustained long-term, indicating a potential need for ongoing maintenance therapy.

Conclusions: Acupuncture is a safe, feasible, and effective complementary therapy for haemodialysis patients. It provides significant benefits for functional capacity and short-term quality of life. These findings support integrating acupuncture into multidisciplinary dialysis care models to enhance evidence-based management of chronic kidney disease.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Disease; Haemodialysis; Acupuncture; Functional Capacity; Quality of Life; Integrative Medicine.

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